

SMART HOMES WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Some people say that the 21st century is the age of artificial intelligence. In the summer of 1956, McCarthy officially proposed the term "artificial intelligence" that lasted up to the present. Artificial intelligence has been in blossom with radiant light on the stage of the mankind and widely set foot in various fields with its on-going expansion.

Artificial Intelligence, or AI, is a new technical science, which is developed with the combination of many subjects. In simple terms, artificial intelligence is to endow machines with human intelligence, simulate human thinking so as to help people solve problems and to realize more advanced applications such as computer-aided human production and living. Artificial intelligence, a branch of computer science, is considered to be one of the three most advanced technologies (Genetic engineering, Nano science and Artificial intelligence) in the 21st century. Artificial intelligence has achieved extremely rapid development in the past 30 years and has been widely used in many academic fields¹.

AI has been increasingly imbedded into people's daily life, such as: more and more well-functioned smartphones, smart watches, unmanned vehicle technology, speech video, facial recognition, text recognition and various AI services such as dialogue and interaction technology; It is indisputable that the continuous development and maturity of these technologies have brought a lot of convenience to people's life. Especially in the field of home design, the emergence of artificial intelligence has greatly improved the efficiency and quality of modern home life. People's demand for products also promotes the continuous progress and development of AI technology, so artificial intelligence will continue to change and affect our home life.

Smart home is a system that combines all kinds of subsystems related to home life through household information management platform with computer, networks and integrated wiring technology. This system has closely linked a variety of home appliances with people's home life, saving efforts, enhancing the utilization of time, and improving the comfort, safety and quality of home life. Home system design is closely combined with artificial intelligence, so that users can enjoy more effective and humanized home experience.

Research and Markets forecast that the global smart home market will grow at an annual rate of 14 per cent over the next five years and reach \$122bn by 2022. It is expected to surge to \$400bn by 2030. According to the analysis, China's smart TV penetration rate in recent years and the trend of the next two years in general is on the rise, and some more common intelligent home appliances such as smart refrigerator, smart washing machine, smart air conditioning, smart TV will also enjoy an increasing penetration rate.

For example, the intelligent sound box products and a whole set of intelligent kitchen products interconnect and communicate, to achieve more friendly interaction, more powerful functions and services. For example, all kitchen electric intelligent products in the kitchen can achieve intelligent voice control by connecting the speakers. Moreover, the powerful interaction ability can also easily realize the complex function of kitchen appliances. in

¹ Li huaqiang, On the Impact of Artificial Intelligence[J]. Information Recording Materials, 18, (2017)

intelligent kitchen, as long as the user prepares the ingredients and inputs instructions or directly use of the function of the recommended recipes, the smart systems will be instantly connected to the cloud platform, search the recipe database, and then automatically move the ingredients to the cooking devices. Reserved cooking and one-key cooking makes it time-saving and trouble-saving for the users. In the future, there may be the emergence of the refrigerator that can identify the freshness of the stored food and to alert the users accordingly, by recording the date that the ingredients were stored in the fridge to remind the user, and display the best edible date, and alert the users about the expired food².

In smart bedrooms, you can give instructions to all kinds of systems to work automatically directly through your smart phone remotely. For instance:

- 1) The switch of intelligent air conditioning; users are able to adjust the required room temperature in advance when they are still outside.
- 2) Users can adjust to the proper indoor light according to the environment and time. Based on the room humidity level to automatically adjust to the appropriate indoor air humidity that suits the human body.
- 3) Users can control their curtains and windows by wireless connections whenever and wherever possible.
- 4) Some studies pointed out that normal people will turn 30 to 60 times during their sleeps. Based on the analysis of the body's dynamic movement and the date generated, the smart bed are able to adjust to the most suitable bed surface state and angle that conforms to human engineering and the user's body structure, allowing users to obtain a more suitable sleep environment. Smart beds can also monitor users' sleep and improve their sleep quality by providing a more suitable sleeping environment through computational analysis.

Artificial intelligence is more widely used in living rooms.

- 1) Smart TV can directly switch channels via voice control. The traditional remote controls are no longer needed. The brightness sensors can detect the light level in the environment and automatically adjust the brightness and color, enhance the users' visual experience.
- 2) Intelligent thermostat sensors monitor the temperature of homes. It evaluates the actual home conditions to adjust the right temperature automatically. Users can have access to the thermostat via mobile phone connections and remotely view and adjust the indoor temperature.
- 3) Lamps are the indispensable part of the living room. The intelligent lamps can adjust themselves according to user's biological clock, to meet various needs of users. Users can also easily operate on the mobile phone for lamp management, in accordance with the requirements of different scenarios to adjust light feeling, building exclusive atmosphere.
- 4) The highest utilized and also the most indispensable part of the living room is probably the sofa. After combining with artificial intelligence, sofa will be more powerful and functional. Equipped with electronic devices, the sofa will be safe and convenient for users. The head rest with automatic adjustment, includes massage function, user can obtain more comfortable experience on sofa.
- 5) Through the phone APP voice control system to control the whole living room appliances, choose a different model to adjust the need of environment condition. For example, if the

² Shen Hua, Current Situation and Prospect of Intelligent Home Ddevelopment [J] Information and Computer.03 (2017)

sleep mode is chosen, then TV, lighting, curtain of the sitting room will be closed automatically. Intelligent electric control system can remotely control and manage the electrical appliances, the user can through electronic devices such as mobile phones, smart panel of household electrical appliances for centralized management, so as to achieve the goal of energy saving, environmental protection, and convenience³.

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence home appliances have greatly facilitated people's daily life, but everything has two sides; the development of artificial intelligence home appliances is also a double-edged sword. The development of smart homes is not aimed at completely overthrowing the old way of life. The use of the smart home brings the user's emotional loss, high cost, high technical requirements, maintenance problems such as weak pertinence and independent initiative is still there. While give users convenient life, therefore, there should be more reflection on the existing problems and better solve or avoid those problems in the future development of smart home appliances. This way smart home appliances could gain market advantage, and gained popularity and development.

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